

A spectral element method for second-order boundary value problems based on the hierarchical Poincaré-Steklov scheme

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Abstract

This paper presents an implementation of the hierarchical Poincaré–Steklov (HPS) spectral element method for the numerical solution of one-dimensional second-order boundary value problems. The method combines a high-order spectral Galerkin discretization with a direct solver based on the hierarchical merging of Dirichlet-to-Neumann (DtN) operators. The computational mesh is represented as a binary tree of intervals, facilitating the implementation of adaptive mesh refinement. Numerical examples verify the implementation of the HPS scheme and confirm its high-order accuracy for smooth solutions.

1 Introduction

We consider the second-order differential equation of the form

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(au - b \frac{du}{dx} \right) + cu = d, \quad (1)$$

where $u(x)$ is the desired solution and $a(x)$, $b(x)$, $c(x)$, and $d(x)$ are sufficiently smooth functions. Equation (1) is defined for $x \in [x_1, x_2] \subset \mathbb{R}$ and is subject to boundary conditions of the form

$$\alpha_1 u(x_1) + \beta_1 u'(x_1) = \gamma_1, \quad (2a)$$

$$\alpha_2 u(x_2) + \beta_2 u'(x_2) = \gamma_2, \quad (2b)$$

where α_i , β_i , and γ_i , for $i = 1, 2$, are prescribed constants.

Equation (1), together with boundary conditions (2a) and (2b), is solved using a spectral element method based on the hierarchical Poincaré–Steklov (HPS) scheme. The HPS scheme represents a direct solver based on operations with Dirichlet-to-Neumann (DtN) operators or their analogues. The original version of the scheme was developed for solving two- and three-dimensional elliptic equations [1–6]. In this paper, we describe the implementation of the HPS scheme for one-dimensional problems.

The computational mesh is built as a binary tree of intervals, where each refinement step bisects a parent interval to create new nodes. The root of the tree is defined by the interval $[x_1, x_2]$ on which the problem is solved. The leaf nodes of the tree represent the mesh elements on which the primary discretization of Eq. (1) is performed. The discretization employs the Galerkin method with basis functions associated with the Gauss–Lobatto quadrature nodes. The primary discretization is used to construct an analogue of the DtN operator for each mesh element and to define a local solution operator that maps the Dirichlet data (i.e., the values at the element endpoints) to the interior nodes of the element.

The HPS scheme is then formulated in three steps. First, the computational mesh is traversed in a bottom-up manner, and for each internal tree node the DtN operator is constructed from the DtN operators of its child nodes. This procedure also yields a solution operator that maps the Dirichlet data of the parent node to the Dirichlet data of its child nodes. Second, the DtN operator of the root node is used together with the boundary conditions to determine the solution at the endpoints x_1 and x_2 . Third, the mesh is traversed in a top-down manner, and the solution operator associated with each internal tree node is used to determine the solution for its child nodes. Finally, the solution operator associated with each leaf node is used to compute the solution within each mesh element.

A detailed description of the HPS scheme is presented in Section 2. Numerical examples verifying the HPS scheme are presented in Section 3.

2 Method description

2.1 Discretization on the leaf nodes

Discretization of Eq. (1) on the leaf nodes (elements) of the computational mesh is performed using a spectral Galerkin method. The procedure is described assuming that each leaf node is mapped onto the reference element $[-1, 1]$. On the reference element, Eq. (1) takes the form

$$\frac{1}{\Delta x} \frac{df}{dx} + cu = d, \quad x \in [-1, 1], \quad (3)$$

where Δx denotes the half-length of the original element, and

$$f = au - \frac{b}{\Delta x} \frac{du}{dx}. \quad (4)$$

To define the basis functions, we introduce the Gauss–Lobatto quadrature nodes x_i , for $1 \leq i \leq n$, on the reference element, with $x_1 = -1$ and $x_n = 1$. The basis functions are defined as the Lagrange polynomials $\varphi_i(x)$ satisfying

$$\varphi_i(x_j) = \delta_{ij}, \quad 1 \leq i, j \leq n.$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta function:

$$\delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i \neq j \\ 1 & \text{if } i = j. \end{cases}$$

Equation (3) is discretized by multiplying with the basis functions and integrating over the element interior:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \varphi_i \frac{df}{dx} dx + \Delta x \int_{-1}^1 \varphi_i (cu - d) dx = 0, \quad (5)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Integrating the first term by parts, we obtain the weak form of Eq. (3):

$$\varphi_i f \Big|_{-1}^1 - \int_{-1}^1 f \frac{d\varphi_i}{dx} dx + \Delta x \int_{-1}^1 \varphi_i (cu - d) dx = 0, \quad (6)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

The solution within the element is approximated by

$$u(x) \approx \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi_i(x) u_i, \quad (7)$$

where u_i denote the solution values at the Gauss–Lobatto nodes.

By applying the Gauss–Lobatto quadrature to evaluate the integrals in Eq. (6), we obtain the following linear system:

$$\varphi_i f \Big|_{-1}^1 + \sum_{j=1}^n M_{ij} u_j = r_i, \quad (8)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq n$, where

$$M_{ij} = -w_j a(x_j) \frac{d\varphi_i}{dx}(x_j) + \sum_{k=1}^n w_k \frac{b(x_k)}{\Delta x} \frac{d\varphi_j}{dx}(x_k) \frac{d\varphi_i}{dx}(x_k) + \Delta x c(x_j) w_j \delta_{ij}, \quad (9)$$

$$r_i = \Delta x d(x_i) w_i \quad (10)$$

where w_i for $1 \leq i \leq n$ are the weights of the Gauss–Lobatto quadrature.

The system (8) can be written in the following form:

$$f(1) + M_{11}u_1 + M_{1n}u_n + \sum_{j=2}^{n-1} M_{1j}u_j = r_1, \quad (11a)$$

$$\sum_{j=2}^{n-1} M_{ij}u_j + M_{i1}u_1 + M_{in}u_n = r_i, \quad \text{for } 2 \leq i \leq n, \quad (11b)$$

$$-f(-1) + M_{n1}u_1 + M_{nn}u_n + \sum_{j=2}^{n-1} M_{nj}u_j = r_n. \quad (11c)$$

After that, Eq. (11b) is solved for u_i , $2 \leq i \leq n-1$, yielding

$$u_i = q_{i1}u_1 + q_{in}u_n + g_i, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-1, \quad (12)$$

where q_{i1} , q_{in} , and g_i are mapping coefficients. Equation (12) represents a local solution operator that maps the Dirichlet data u_1 and u_n to the internal degrees of freedom within the element.

By substituting Eq. (12) into Eqs. (11a) and (11c) and rearranging, we obtain

$$f_1 = \delta_{11}u_1 + \delta_{12}u_n + \eta_1, \quad (13a)$$

$$f_2 = \delta_{21}u_1 + \delta_{22}u_n + \eta_2, \quad (13b)$$

where $f_1 = f(1)$, $f_2 = f(-1)$ and δ_{11} , δ_{12} , δ_{21} , δ_{22} , η_1 , η_2 are mapping coefficients. Eqs. (13) map the Dirichlet data u_1 and u_n to the flux values at the endpoints of the element. From this perspective, Eqs. (13) represent an analogue of the Dirichlet-to-Neumann (DtN) operator formulated at the element level.

2.2 Construction of the solution operator

Having constructed the DtN operators for each element, we proceed to construct the global solution operator. To this end, the computational mesh is traversed in a bottom-up manner and for each internal tree node the DtN operator is constructed from the DtN operators of its child nodes. This procedure is described in what follows.

Consider two adjacent intervals corresponding to the child nodes of an internal node in the computational mesh. Let the DtN operator associated with the left interval be written as

$$f_1^L = \delta_{11}^L u_1^L + \delta_{12}^L u_2^L + \eta_1^L, \quad (14a)$$

$$f_2^L = \delta_{21}^L u_1^L + \delta_{22}^L u_2^L + \eta_2^L, \quad (14b)$$

and let the DtN operator associated with the right interval be written as

$$f_1^R = \delta_{11}^R u_1^R + \delta_{12}^R u_2^R + \eta_1^R, \quad (15a)$$

$$f_2^R = \delta_{21}^R u_1^R + \delta_{22}^R u_2^R + \eta_2^R. \quad (15b)$$

Here, u_1^L and u_2^L denote the solution values at the endpoints of the left interval, and u_1^R and u_2^R denote the solution values at the endpoints of the right interval. Note that u_1^L and u_2^R correspond to the Dirichlet data of the parent mesh node.

Using the continuity of the solution at the common point of the two intervals, we obtain

$$f_2^L = f_1^R. \quad (16)$$

Using Eq. (16) together with Eqs. (14b) and (15a), we obtain

$$\delta_{21}^L u_1^L + \delta_{22}^L u_2^L + \eta_2^L = \delta_{11}^R u_1^R + \delta_{12}^R u_2^R + \eta_1^R, \quad (17)$$

which, after rearranging, yields

$$u = q_1 u_1^L + q_2 u_2^R + g_{12} \quad (18)$$

where $u := u_2^L = u_1^R$ and

$$q_1 = -\frac{\delta_{21}^L}{\delta_{22}^L - \delta_{11}^R}, \quad q_2 = \frac{\delta_{12}^R}{\delta_{22}^L - \delta_{11}^R}, \quad g_{12} = \frac{\eta_1^R - \eta_2^L}{\delta_{22}^L - \delta_{11}^R}.$$

Equation (18) represents the solution operator associated with the considered parent node of the mesh. It maps the Dirichlet data of the parent node to the solution value at the interface between the child nodes and therefore enables the reconstruction of the Dirichlet data of the child nodes.

Equation (18) can now be used to construct the DtN operator for the parent mesh node. For this, Eq. (18) is substituted into Eqs. (14a) and (15b). The resulting DtN operator for the parent mesh node is given by

$$f_1^L = \delta_{11} u_1^L + \delta_{12} u_2^R + \eta_1, \quad (19a)$$

$$f_2^R = \delta_{21} u_1^L + \delta_{22} u_2^R + \eta_2. \quad (19b)$$

where

$$\delta_{11} = \delta_{12}^L q_1 + \delta_{11}^L,$$

$$\delta_{12} = \delta_{12}^L q_2,$$

$$\delta_{21} = \delta_{21}^R q_1,$$

$$\delta_{22} = \delta_{21}^R q_2 + \delta_{22}^R$$

and

$$\eta_1 = \delta_{12}^L g_{12} + \eta_1^L,$$

$$\eta_2 = \delta_{21}^R g_{12} + \eta_2^R.$$

The operator in Eq. (19) maps the Dirichlet data of the parent node to the corresponding flux values at its endpoints. From this perspective, this operator represents

an analogue of the DtN operator for the parent node, constructed from the DtN operators of its child nodes.

The construction of the solution operators, such as in Eq. (18), and the DtN operators, such as in Eq. (19), is carried out for all internal nodes as the computational mesh is traversed in a bottom-up manner. The collection of all solution and DtN operators associated with the internal nodes of the mesh is referred to as the global solution operator.

2.3 Solution procedure

Once the global solution operator is constructed, the desired solution is obtained in three steps. First, the DtN operator of the root node is combined with the boundary conditions (2a) and (2b) to compute the solution values $u(x_1)$ and $u(x_2)$ at the endpoints of the interval on which the problem is solved.

After that, the computational mesh is traversed in a top-down manner, and the solution operator at each internal tree node is used to compute the solution values at the endpoints of its child nodes. For a given internal tree node, the solution operator is defined by Eq. (18). This operator is first used to compute the solution value at the interface between the child nodes. This value, together with the Dirichlet data of the parent node, provides the necessary information to construct the Dirichlet data for the child nodes.

After constructing the Dirichlet data on all nodes of the tree, the local solution operators defined on the leaf nodes are used to compute the complete solution within the mesh elements. For a given leaf node, the local solution operator is given by Eq. (12). This operator defines the mapping from the Dirichlet data to the internal nodes of the element.

2.4 Adaptive mesh refinement

The structure of the HPS scheme naturally supports the use of adaptive mesh refinement. The computational mesh can be refined by bisecting leaf nodes or coarsened by removing leaf nodes that are children of an internal tree node. In both operations, interpolation is required to transfer the solution between parent and child nodes.

Assume that a parent node is mapped to the reference element $[-1, 1]$ and the solution is approximated as defined in Eq. (7). The children nodes correspond to the subintervals $[-1, 0]$ and $[0, 1]$ of the parent node and are each mapped to the reference element $[-1, 1]$. Let u_i^L and u_i^R , for $1 \leq i \leq n$, denote the solution values at the Gauss–Lobatto nodes of the left and right child elements, respectively.

During refinement, these values are obtained by interpolating the solution from the parent node. Using Eq. (7), we obtain

$$u_i^L = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \left(\frac{x_i - 1}{2} \right) u_k, \quad (20a)$$

$$u_i^R = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \left(\frac{x_i + 1}{2} \right) u_k, \quad (20b)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq n$, with x_i being the Gauss–Lobatto quadrature nodes.

During coarsening, the values u_i^L and u_i^R are used to reconstruct the values of the solution at the parent node. This is carried out using an integral projection procedure [7], leading to the expression

$$w_i u_i = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_i \left(\frac{x_k - 1}{2} \right) w_k u_k^L + \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_i \left(\frac{x_k + 1}{2} \right) w_k u_k^R, \quad (21)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq n$, with w_i being the weights of the Gauss-Lobatto quadrature.

Equations (20) and (21) are used to transfer the solution between parent and child nodes during mesh refinement and coarsening.

3 Numerical examples

In this section, we present numerical results demonstrating the performance of the HPS method for solving second-order boundary-value problems. All numerical experiments were performed using the implementation of the HPS method provided by the open-source package *hpsolver* [8].

3.1 Boundary layer

We first consider a boundary-layer problem. Specifically, we solve

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(u - b \frac{du}{dx} \right) = 0, \quad (22)$$

on the interval $[0, 1]$ with $b = 0.1$, subject to the boundary conditions

$$u(0) = 1, \quad u(1) = 0. \quad (23)$$

This problem admits an exact solution given by

$$u_{\text{ex}} = \frac{e^{x/b} - e^{1/b}}{1 - e^{1/b}}. \quad (24)$$

To assess the accuracy of the numerical solution, we consider the discrete error

$$e_h = u^h - u_{\text{ex}}^h, \quad (25)$$

where u^h denotes the numerical solution and u_{ex}^h denotes the projection of the exact solution onto the finite-element space.

To quantify the discrete error between the numerical and exact solutions, the following discrete error norms are introduced:

$$\|e_h\|_{L^\infty} = \max |e_h|, \quad (26a)$$

$$\|e_h\|_{L^2} = \left(\int_0^1 e_h^2 dx \right)^{1/2}. \quad (26b)$$

The maximum norm in Eq. (26a) is computed by taking the maximum absolute error over all nodes of the computational mesh. The integral in Eq. (26b) is evaluated by summing the element contributions, each computed using the Gauss–Lobatto quadrature.

Table 1 Errors and orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the boundary-layer problem, using $n = 4$ Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element and different numbers of elements (N_e).

N_e	L^∞ error	L^∞ order	L^2 error	L^2 order
8	1.326E-04	-	4.067E-05	-
16	5.530E-06	4.58	1.401E-06	4.86
32	1.973E-07	4.81	4.495E-08	4.96
64	6.556E-09	4.91	1.414E-09	4.99
128	2.108E-10	4.96	4.427E-11	5.00

Table 2 Errors and orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the boundary-layer problem, using $n = 5$ Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element and different numbers of elements (N_e).

N_e	L^∞ error	L^∞ order	L^2 error	L^2 order
4	2.127E-04	-	8.547E-05	-
8	6.260E-06	5.09	1.800E-06	5.57
16	1.347E-07	5.54	3.071E-08	5.87
32	2.467E-09	5.77	4.911E-10	5.97
64	4.166E-11	5.89	7.727E-12	5.99

Table 3 Errors and orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the boundary-layer problem, using $n = 6$ Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element and different numbers of elements (N_e).

N_e	L^∞ error	L^∞ order	L^2 error	L^2 order
2	7.132E-04	-	4.039E-04	-
4	1.756E-05	5.34	6.976E-06	5.86
8	2.476E-07	6.15	7.297E-08	6.58
16	2.602E-09	6.57	6.211E-10	6.88
32	2.346E-11	6.79	4.978E-12	6.96

Tables 1–3 present the errors and observed orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the boundary-layer problem for different numbers of Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element. In all cases, the observed convergence orders exceed the theoretical rates associated with the degree of the approximating polynomials. While superconvergent behavior is sometimes observed in spectral element methods, the origin of this behavior in the HPS method remains an open question and requires further investigation.

3.2 Manufactured solution

The second test problem is based on the method of manufactured solutions. Specifically, we solve the equation

$$-\frac{d^2u}{dx^2} + u = \sin(2\pi x) (4\pi^2 + 1), \quad (27)$$

on the interval $[0, 1]$, subject to boundary conditions

$$u(0) = u(1) = 0. \quad (28)$$

The exact solution of this problem is given by $u = \sin(2\pi x)$.

Table 4 Errors and orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the manufactured-solution problem, using $n = 4$ Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element and different numbers of elements (N_e).

N_e	L^∞ error	L^∞ order	L^2 error	L^2 order
4	4.270E-04	-	3.198E-04	-
8	1.446E-05	4.88	9.682E-06	5.05
16	4.610E-07	4.97	3.003E-07	5.01
32	1.448E-08	4.99	9.367E-09	5.00
64	4.530E-10	5.00	2.926E-10	5.00

Table 5 Errors and orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the manufactured-solution problem, using $n = 5$ Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element and different numbers of elements (N_e).

N_e	L^∞ error	L^∞ order	L^2 error	L^2 order
4	1.668E-05	-	1.268E-05	-
8	3.372E-07	5.63	1.974E-07	6.01
16	5.580E-09	5.92	3.083E-09	6.00
32	8.843E-11	5.98	4.816E-11	6.00
64	1.209E-12	6.19	7.808E-13	5.95

Table 6 Errors and orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the manufactured-solution problem, using $n = 6$ Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element and different numbers of elements (N_e).

N_e	L^∞ error	L^∞ order	L^2 error	L^2 order
2	2.784E-05	-	2.368E-05	-
4	6.815E-07	5.35	5.097E-07	5.54
8	6.516E-09	6.71	4.000E-09	6.99
16	5.334E-11	6.93	3.129E-11	7.00
32	4.587E-13	6.86	2.717E-13	6.85

The error between the numerical and exact solutions is quantified using the same error norms as those used in Section 3.1. Tables 4–6 present the errors and observed orders of convergence of the HPS scheme for the manufactured-solution problem for different numbers of Gauss–Lobatto nodes per element. As in Section 3.1, the observed convergence orders exceed the theoretical rates associated with the degree of the approximating polynomials. These results provide further verification of the implementation of the HPS scheme and confirm that the discretization exhibits the expected high-order accuracy for smooth solutions, while also displaying superconvergent behavior in the tests considered here.

4 Conclusion

An implementation of the hierarchical Poincaré–Steklov (HPS) spectral element method for one-dimensional second-order boundary value problems has been presented. The method is a direct solver based on the hierarchical merging of Dirichlet-to-Neumann (DtN) operators associated with nested intervals organized in a binary tree. On the leaf intervals, the solution is discretized using a high-order spectral Galerkin method based on Gauss–Lobatto quadrature nodes.

The solution procedure consists of three steps. First, a solution operator is constructed through the recursive merging of DtN operators on the internal nodes of the tree. Second, the boundary conditions are applied to determine the solution values at the endpoints of the computational interval. Third, the solution operator is applied to compute the solution throughout the internal and leaf nodes of the tree.

The resulting scheme possesses a high order of accuracy and is well suited for adaptive mesh refinement due to the hierarchical organization of the computational mesh. Numerical experiments were performed to verify the implementation of the method and confirm its high-order accuracy. In all cases, the observed convergence rates exceeded the theoretical predictions, indicating superconvergent behavior of the method.

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